

Benchmarking WebAssembly for Embedded Systems*

KONRAD MORON, Computer Science and Mathematics, Hochschule München University of Applied Sciences, Munich, Germany and Technische Universität München, Munich, Germany

STEFAN WALLENTOWITZ, Computer Science and Mathematics, Hochschule München University of Applied Sciences, Munich, Germany

WebAssembly is a modern, low-level virtual machine with designed for improved application performance in web browsers. Recently, WebAssembly gained interest for its use outside the web, for example as a replacement for serverless container runtimes. A number of non-web WebAssembly implementations are actively supported, some of which target microcontrollers, IoT devices, and embedded systems. Such hardware platforms have strict resource constraints which may render the usage of WebAssembly impossible or too costly, for example due to its performance overhead and memory requirements. However, it is currently unclear what performance to expect of WebAssembly on low-resource microcontrollers compared to machine code and alternative application virtual machines. To answer this question, we evaluated the processing overhead and memory characteristics of WebAssembly application virtual machines on microcontrollers, and compare it to native execution, and the established application virtual machines: MicroPython and Lua. Furthermore, we analyzed the feature-set and architecture of the WebAssembly implementations in more detail, and measured the performance impact different runtime features have. We found that WebAssembly, despite its high extensibility and versatility in supported source languages, application paradigms, and target hardware, delivers very competitive performance. We conclude that WebAssembly can find wider industry usage for embedded systems and could replace other more costly or less flexible virtualization techniques, such as Java.

CCS Concepts: • **Computer systems organization** → **Embedded software**; • **Software and its engineering** → **Interpreters**; Runtime environments; Scripting languages; • **General and reference** → *Evaluation*.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: application virtual machine, edge computing, containerization

1 Introduction

Application development for low-resource embedded systems faces several challenges [36]: Language features, such as scheduling, concurrency, or dynamic memory management, are constrained or unavailable; The hardware/software interface of different embedded systems are heterogeneous, making software non-portable between devices [69]; And ensuring security and safety of a platform is challenging, especially when multiple, potentially interfering programs are running on one device, as most embedded systems do not isolate software faults [37, 50]. Software for datacenters, cloud-platforms, or workstations avoids these challenges partly because of strict standardization and established abstraction layers such as operating systems.

One option to overcome these challenges are application virtual machines [63]. Application virtual machines execute programs of either a virtual instruction set or source code, each by implementing the middleware for translation between the semantics of the underlying hardware and the implemented virtual machine. Application

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Authors' Contact Information: Konrad Moron, Computer Science and Mathematics, Hochschule München University of Applied Sciences, Munich, Germany and Technische Universität München, Munich, Bayern, Germany; e-mail: Konrad.moron@tum.de; Stefan Wallentowitz, Computer Science and Mathematics, Hochschule München University of Applied Sciences, Munich, Germany; e-mail: stefan.wallentowitz@hm.edu.

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virtual machines increase the flexibility of software development, as they no longer have to account for the differences of heterogeneous target hardware [23]. Since programs are executed virtually, applications can be isolated from each other by checking the legality of code at runtime. This effectively prevents unprivileged accesses to memory and other resources, and protects the system from faulty or malicious applications [50]. Application virtual machines are not widely used on low-resource systems because they incur considerable processing and memory overhead compared to native execution. This can be especially problematic on embedded devices, which may not have the required memory. For example, the virtual machine used on "Java Cards", a type of smart card capable of executing Java, is heavily modified compared to established Java implementations, so that it can run on the hardware of a smart card. While being an established industry solution for smart cards, Java Card is not suited as a general framework for arbitrary embedded system applications as it is proprietary and designed for secure elements [49].

WebAssembly (WASM) is a modern, low-level bytecode application virtual machine that is gaining momentum and interest for its use on embedded systems and IoT devices [61, 73]. Applications are written in one of many source languages and compiled to WASM before being executed by a virtual machine. WebAssembly's low-level semantics allow it to be support a wide variety of source languages and heterogeneous hardware platforms. Being a bytecode-level instruction set that multiple languages can be compiled to, it is similar to the well-known Java virtual machine (JVM) [41]. Java's higher-level semantics have made it difficult to use on constrained hardware.

The performance of microcontroller-compatible WebAssembly implementations have not been compared with alternative application virtual machines that also target low-resource microcontrollers. Furthermore, it is not clear which WebAssembly runtime offers the best performance on embedded systems for typical workloads, and how they should be configured to yield optimal performance regarding memory use and computational speed.

We address these questions by evaluating the features and performance of available, microcontroller-focused WebAssembly runtimes. We further compare modern WebAssembly *interpreter* runtimes with established application virtual machine interpreters that are targeted at embedded systems, in particular MicroPython [17] and Lua [32]. Finally, we examine *binary translation* runtime options for WebAssembly, which tackle the trade-off of portability and performance.

1.1 Structure of this Work

Section 3 gives an overview of the WebAssembly module model and execution model. Evaluated application virtual machines, which include different WebAssembly implementations and other runtimes, are outlined in Section 4. The interpretation execution modes of each runtime are evaluated for computational and memory overhead in Section 5. We then take a more detailed look at WebAssembly runtimes on embedded systems and the impact of ahead-of-time compilation on performance in Section 6. Section 7 concludes our work.

2 Related Work

Application virtual machines are a well-established technology for executing code with high portability and security. As introduced before, the Java adoption for resource-constraint systems JavaCard has been introduced in 1996. JavaCard is a subset of Java, tailored for smart cards and despite ambitions from the JavaCard Forum to make it a general-purpose platform for the internet of things [1], it has not seen widespread adoption. Embedded Java implementations such as JamaicaVM [2] are targeting very specific use-cases and are generally less well accessible.

As popular alternatives to Java, Lua and MicroPython have gained some traction in embedded systems. Lua is a lightweight, embeddable scripting language that is used in a wide range of applications, from embedded systems [20] to game development [33]. MicroPython is a lean implementation of Python 3 for microcontrollers [16] that has seen some popularity in IoT applications [24].

WebAssembly is different in that it is a pure virtual machine, not tied to a specific programming language. It is designed to be a universal target for languages like C, C++, Rust, Go, AssemblyScript and others. While originally designed for the browser environment, WebAssembly has seen adoption in non-web environments [43, 48] and in the last years also on embedded systems [40, 56, 69, 74]. Beyond the application of WebAssembly in IoT deployments and edge computing, there is also research on how to improve the performance of WebAssembly interpreters, the code generation [60] and even hardware acceleration [38, 59].

With the variety of options and the broad availability of open source implementations, it is desirable to have a comparison of WebAssembly runtimes as well as a comparison to established application virtual machines. There has been work on the analysis of MicroPython performance on embedded system [34] and in particular in comparison to natively compiled languages [51], and only very limited comparison of Lua and MicroPython [54].

Over the recent years, WebAssembly benchmarking has come to focus, inside the browser [35, 77] and also increasingly outside the browser: [70] characterizes available standalone, i.e. non-web WebAssembly virtual machines and profiles them on high-performance workstation for comparison. Their work is not focused on WASM's performance and characteristics on embedded systems but a general, non-web environment. [29] empirically studies WebAssembly binaries gathered from multiple sources. Their work studies real-world WASM binaries for attributes such as source language or memory layout. [61] outlines the state of WebAssembly on non-web environments, and compares the performance of standalone WebAssembly to web-browser's execution engines for WASM and JavaScript. [22] analyzes WebAssembly use as a serverless container runtime for low-latency domains such as edge-computing. [28] are benchmarking on mobile/IoT devices, but there mobile/IoT devices are smartphone class with a lot different capabilities and characteristics.

Contrary to the state of the art, we provide an extensive comparison of MicroPython, Lua and WebAssembly for embedded systems with established benchmarks for embedded systems. To our knowledge, there has been no comparable work.

3 WebAssembly

WebAssembly is a modern binary instruction set for a virtual stack-based machine [73]. It was originally designed as a fast, portable and small virtual code format for use in web browsers in conjunction with JavaScript. However, it is not restricted to the original use case, as each environment WebAssembly is executed on can provide an API for interaction. For example, web browsers offer an execution environment with functionality for the interoperability of JavaScript with WASM [68]. Similarly, the WebAssembly System Interface (WASI) acts as a general abstraction layer for use in multiple non-web environments [25].

A WebAssembly application consists of a set of modules, all of which declare imported and exported items, such as functions, global variables, tables and memories. Using exports, a module can make functionality available to the runtime environment, also called the *embedder*. Using imports, a module can interact with the embedder, for example by opening and writing files using corresponding imported functions. Because WebAssembly is a stack-based instruction architecture, operations consume their arguments from the stack and push their output to the stack. Note that the stack is implicit, and an execution environment might not use an actual stack for its implementation. Next to the stack, WASM modules have byte-addressable vectors called *memories*, tables that contain values of reference type for indirect dispatch, and per-module global variables that can be modified and read by code. A notable attribute of WASM is that it runs inside a memory-isolated environment and a module's semantics and structure are type-checked for soundness. For instance, the signature of a function is ensured to match the call site's assumptions. Unlike most other bytecode formats, all of WASM's control instructions target well-defined structures, mirroring lexical control flow. Upon entering new scopes, such as if/else blocks or loops, new labels get introduced to the execution state. Control flow instructions and branches can then only jump to labels currently in scope, and not to arbitrary bytecode positions. The semantics of each label is based on its

```
int add (int first, int second) {
    return first + second;
}
```

```
(module
  (type (;1;) (func (param i32 i32) (result
    ↪ i32)))
  (func $add (type 1) (param i32 i32) (result
    ↪ i32)
    local.get 1
    local.get 0
    i32.add)
  (memory (;0;) 2)
  (export "memory" (memory 0))
  (export "add" (func $add)))
```

Listing 1. Add.c and Add.wasm

lexical environment: For blocks and if/else constructs the label points to the end of each construct, while loops are labeled with the beginning of the loop.

WebAssembly bytecode can be displayed in *WebAssembly text format* (wat) which formats a module’s abstract syntax as s-expressions. We can convert between WASM bytecode and the text format, the latter being easier for humans to read and work with. A simple C-program with its WASM compilation result formatted in wat is shown in Listing 1.

WebAssembly is not only designed to be platform-independent, but it is also independent of the source language it can be compiled from. This allows for a wide variety of source languages to support WASM compilation and interoperation [13]. WebAssembly’s low-level nature and the absence of garbage collection or a memory model make it more popular as a target for low-level languages like C, rather than for feature-rich, high-level languages [29, 58]. The language agnostic semantics of WebAssembly separate it from interpreted languages. Instead, WASM is an intermediate format, similar to Java bytecode [41], that can fit the requirements of many source languages and target platforms. Unlike Java bytecode, WebAssembly supports a wider range of source languages [13]. The JVM was originally designed for the execution of Java programs and supports high-level constructs such as dynamic dispatch and classes [41]. As a result, popular languages targeting Java bytecode make use of similar, dynamic or object-oriented features [66]. With the ability to virtualize programs in existing languages, the use cases of WebAssembly overlap with universal virtualization technologies such as containerization and operating systems [46].

4 Evaluated Runtimes

As motivated earlier, the goal of this work is to evaluate the performance of promising WebAssembly runtimes for embedded systems and systematically compare them to other established application virtual machines. The baseline for the comparison is native code, and in this work we in particular focus on embedded benchmarks written in C. As our interest is in particular in the properties of application virtual machines, we do not consider other native code runtimes such as TinyGo [4] or Rust for Embedded [7, 57].

For the selection of the runtimes, we have set a few criteria: The runtimes must be open source, so that we can evaluate their performance and features in a reproducible way. They must be actively maintained, and most importantly must be targeted at baremetal embedded systems to allow for a good portability and to separate the effects from an operating system and the runtime.

Both [70] and [69] identified five standalone WebAssembly runtimes, and [14] reports the six most popular standalone WebAssembly runtimes. In total, we considered the following WASM application virtual machines for evaluation:

Wasmtime: Wasmtime [9] is Bytecode Alliance’s standalone high-performance runtime. It uses the Cranelift [8] code generator to emit native machine code. Since Wasmtime does not support ARM-32 or RISC-V, and requires an operating system, we excluded it from our evaluation.

Wasmer: Wasmer [71] supports Cranelift, LLVM [42], and a single-pass JiT compiler for the high-performance execution of WebAssembly code. It also requires an operating system and currently only supports x86, aarch64, and RV-64, which are not implemented by most microcontrollers.

Wizard: Wizard [65] is a standalone WebAssembly research interpreter. Unfortunately, it is not easy to retarget it to most embedded systems as it is written in its own language, Virgil, and currently only support x86 targets.

Wasm3: Wasm3 [67] is a standalone WASM runtime that supports a wide range of ISA’s, including RISC-V and ARM-32, does not depend on an operating system, and has minimal memory requirements. It purposefully supports embedded systems and achieves its low memory requirements by opting for a simple interpreter, instead of compiling WebAssembly to native code. We included Wasm3 in our evaluation.

WAMR: WebAssembly Micro Runtime [11] is Bytecode Alliance’s lightweight standalone runtime. It complements Wasmtime by targeting small, low-resource platforms, like embedded systems, IoT- or edge-devices. It offers native compilation features, which can be optionally enabled depending on available resources. Because WAMR can run directly on hardware, with no operating system, and has low resource requirements, we included it in our evaluation. WAMR offers the following execution modes: A fast- and classic- interpreter, AoT-compilation, and fast- as well as llvm-JiT modes. We evaluate both interpreters and AoT-compilation.

WasmEdge: WasmEdge [12] targets cloud, edge- and serverless computing platforms. It is a high-performance runtime that supports just-in-time and ahead-of-time compilation to native machine code. It has support for RV64 and Arm, but requires an operating system or microkernel to run. Because WasmEdge does not support running bare-metal on a microcontroller, and requires at least 4GB of RAM when using a microkernel, we excluded it from evaluation.

Wazero: Wazero [64] is a standalone WebAssembly runtime written in Go. While not depending on any external libraries, such as Cranelift or LLVM, Go does not support compiling to bare-metal architectures [26], so we could not evaluate it for embedded systems.

WAVM: WAVM [5] uses LLVM to compile WebAssembly modules to native machine code. It supports Windows, MacOS, and Linux. Because it requires an operating system, we did not include it in our evaluation.

WARDuino: WARDuino [27] is a straight-forward in-place interpreter implementation, which is interesting for its debugging capabilities. It self-reports to be 36 times slower than wasm3 [39], which may make it uncompetitive with alternative runtimes.

WasmI: WasmI [21] is a lightweight WebAssembly interpreter for constrained systems. It is written in Rust and supports the official WebAssembly C API [72].

Of available standalone WASM runtimes, WAMR, Wasm3, WasmI, and WARDuino are suitable for embedded systems. Of these, WAMR and Wasm3 are the most widely used and dominate WasmI and WARDuino in memory usage/execution speed metrics. In addition, we analyzed Lua [30] and MicroPython [16], which are established application virtual machines for microcontrollers [6, 50, 55]. The compared application virtual machines with their exact version used for our evaluation are laid out in Table 1. We compared the performance of all application virtual machines and outline the feature-set, and architecture of selected runtimes in more detail for the reader.

In the remain of this section, we will provide an overview of the architecture of selected runtimes, and discuss their features and limitations. This is useful as a general reference and to understand the results of the evaluation in the following sections.

Table 1. Runtime Characteristics

Application-VM	GitHub Stars	Evaluated Version	Initial Release
Lua	8.1K	v5.4.4 (0x5d708c3f)	1993
MicroPython	18.5K	v1.20.0 (0x294baf52)	2014
Wasm3	7K	v0.5.0 (0x772f8f46)	2020
WAMR	4.6K	v1.2.2 (0xf69ff705)	2019
WARDuino	84	v0.6.1 (0x0c7f92a)	2022
Wasmi	1.7K	v0.40.0 (0xf384f28)	2018

4.1 WebAssembly Micro Runtime

The WebAssembly Micro Runtime is a standalone WebAssembly implementation by Bytecode Alliance that targets bare-metal, low resource targets [11]. It is fully compliant to the current WebAssembly MVP by supporting all specified features. WAMR also supports multiple unspecified and post-MVP features that developers can make use of, making it one of the most versatile runtimes for constrained targets. WebAssembly being a recent development, WebAssembly Micro Runtime has a short history with an initial release in 2019, and version 1.0.0 being published in 2022 [11].

4.1.1 Features. Highlights of WAMR’s feature set for the use on embedded systems, especially compared to Wasm3, include [11]:

- (1) JiT compilation: Eager- and lazy JiT compilation of WebAssembly functions leveraging LLVM in WAMR’s ‘llvm-JiT’ mode, or a small-footprint ‘fast-JiT’ mode. WAMR supports a tiered JiT, which first executed code using the fast-JiT mode, and concurrently optimizes them with LLVM.
- (2) AOT compilation: Allows compiling WebAssembly modules to object files containing native machine code ahead of execution.
- (3) Libc bindings: Allows WebAssembly modules to import libc or WASI functions that are implemented by the target.
- (4) Intermodule dependencies: WAMR automatically resolves imports and exports across loaded modules.
- (5) WebAssembly threading support: Implements and resolves *pthread* or *wasi-thread* imports.
- (6) In Place Execution: AOT modules can be executed from flash storage.
- (7) Posix Socket support: WebAssembly modules can import wasi socket functions.
- (8) WebAssembly application frameworks: Supplemental frameworks built on top of WAMR for managing and running applications.

The ability to automatically bind exported WebAssembly functions to the imports of another module provides a mechanism for secure program interaction, as each module is executed within its own sandbox. This effectively allows for secure, automatic inter-program communication without the need of an operating system.

4.1.2 Architecture. WebAssembly Micro Runtime splits its internal state into modules, module instances, execution environments, and ancillary data structures [10, 11, 75, 76]. Figure 1 visualizes the most important relations of WAMR’s internals. WebAssembly is executed with reference to an execution environment that owns the current WebAssembly stack. The execution environment references a module instance, that owns instantiated WebAssembly linear memory, functions, and global data. The module instance refers to a loaded WebAssembly module, which owns the compiled function code, metadata such as exports, imports, and function types. The data owned by a WebAssembly module does not typically change during execution, and it can be shared between

Fig. 1. WebAssembly Micro Runtime architecture

multiple module instances. When enabling JiT or AoT support, a WASM module may own the native code generated during compilation. WAMR's AoT and JiT compiler leverage LLVM to compile WebAssembly modules into machine instructions for any supported backend. WebAssembly Micro Runtime's architecture allows developers to execute multiple loaded WebAssembly modules, which coexist in memory, concurrently. Figure 1 omits or merges many references between data structures that are present in the actual implementation for brevity.

The linear memory region owned by a WebAssembly module instance is typically further divided into sections according to conventions by the WebAssembly compiler and linker. A linear memory region is typically subdivided into a data region, an auxiliary stack that is used to pass data structures to functions, an optional app heap managed by WAMR should the WebAssembly module not host its own allocator, and the heap owned and managed by the WebAssembly module itself. The layout of memory accessible to WebAssembly applications is further detailed in Figure 2.

Whether the app heap or the module's internal heap is used to allocate dynamic memory depends on how the WebAssembly module was compiled. If developers import native functions from `libc`, such as `malloc`, when linking WebAssembly code, WAMR will execute in what we refer to as *semihosted* mode. In this mode, `libc` is implemented in native C that will be linked against corresponding imports of the WASM module. This has the advantage that memory usage and processing overhead is lowered, but reduces portability of WebAssembly programs, as they are relying on imported functions. When this mode is not used, `libc` is implemented as WebAssembly bytecode and manages its own heap. In this case, WAMR has to allocate full pages of memory to the module instance, which introduces memory overhead since each page's length is 64KiB. In semihosted mode, WAMR uses the exported section labels to reduce page length below a multiple of 64KiB, which requires non-spec compliant assumptions about the compiled WASM module. The disadvantage of semihosting is that the module can't be executed should `libc` bindings not be available on the embedder.

In addition to linear memory regions and global data, WebAssembly code is executed using an operand stack that is owned by WAMR's execution environment. When WebAssembly invokes a native import, or when a native

Fig. 2. WebAssembly memory layout in WAMR

function invokes a WebAssembly export, the arguments are copied between the native- and WebAssembly stack. Note that the execution stack is not necessarily structured as described in the WebAssembly specification: when using the interpreter in the 'fast' configuration, the execution stack contains register files that each operation indexes into.

4.2 Discussion

WAMR offers a variety of optional features that make it a compelling choice for use on low-resource systems [69]. Other microcontroller compatible WebAssembly runtimes, like Wasm3 [67], take a more minimalistic approach, only implementing the core WASM feature set, basic WASI bindings, and not supporting JiT or AOT compilation and automatic inter-module dependencies.

Advanced features of WAMR, especially JiT and AOT compilation, may also undo the security and safety advantages of WebAssembly's application sandboxing and inherent memory isolation. When using either feature, the runtime no longer interprets virtual WebAssembly instructions but directly executes native code. A malicious or faulty WebAssembly module may compromise the entire system when JiT or AOT compilation is used. Historically, JiT compilers offer a greater attack surface to errors or malicious attacks, and it is difficult to ensure JiT compiled code is properly isolated from the rest of the system [?].

For example, if WAMR's native code compiler does not generate proper bounds checking on WebAssembly store instructions, a faulty module could write to another module's memory and cause it to crash. Developers will not always be able to utilize these features, especially in safety- and security critical domains.

WAMR benefits from the platform- and language independent design of WebAssembly, making application development very flexible. WebAssembly is designed to suit a variety of target platforms such as web browsers, cloud devices, embedded systems, and more. This is achieved by specifying a low-level instruction set and memory hierarchy that mirrors many native RISC instruction set architectures. Applications from languages such as C, C++, JavaScript, Python, and more, can be compiled to WebAssembly - although language specific features need to be compiled and included in the resulting module or resolved through imports at runtime. WebAssembly

virtualization on embedded systems allows developers to build applications by combining languages from different domains such as edge computing, compute-heavy tasks, networking, cryptography, etc. WebAssembly imposes minimal restrictions on virtualized applications due to its language-agnostic, low level semantics [13].

However, WebAssembly can also incur both memory and processing overhead [69]. WASM instructions perform simple computations, which requires more bytecodes to be executed to complete complex tasks and thus incurs a higher interpretation overhead [52]. By not specifying abstract language features, WebAssembly modules may need to include their own runtime, such as a memory allocator, which increases module size and memory usage [61]. Lastly, WebAssembly memory regions are allocated in multiples of 64KB: tasks that may require less memory will be executed with unused memory, unless runtime-specific features are used to lower memory region size. Some of these restrictions can be mitigated by WAMR, for example by use of the semihosted mode (see subsection 5.2).

4.3 Wasm3

Wasm3 [67] is a standalone WebAssembly interpreter that also targets microcontrollers and embedded systems. It can be used in place of WebAssembly Micro Runtime as it also has a small memory footprint, efficient interpreter, and few program dependencies. Wasm3 is largely developed and maintained by one person, who authored over 70% of total GitHub commits.

4.3.1 Features. Wasm3 offers fewer features than WebAssembly Micro Runtime, the author focuses on implementing a very optimized interpreter instead of developing features such as AoT or JiT compilation. Not all WebAssembly core proposals are implemented by Wasm3, 5 out of 8 standardized and finished WebAssembly proposals are not yet implemented, including the reference type extension that allows for function reference manipulation. Despite its philosophy, Wasm3 offers some additional features on top of basic WebAssembly support:

- (1) Lightweight codebase: Few dependencies and a tiny codebase make Wasm3 easy to manually extend and modify.
- (2) Libc bindings: Wasm3 ships with WASI bindings and implementations of many C library functions that can be dynamically linked at runtime.
- (3) Customized interpreter configuration: The interpreter can be configured by adjusting data structures and optimization settings, allowing developers to customize Wasm3 to target hardware.

4.3.2 Architecture. Internally, Wasm3 assigns data to *M3Runtime*, *M3Module*, and *M3Function* structs. Wasm3's API consists of utility functions that take a pointer to either of these opaque structs and modify or extract content. For example, to link a new native function, the host calls *m3_LinkRawFunction*, providing it with the module to link against. Separating runtime data into structs that are passed via pointers allows the host program to execute WebAssembly code in parallel, similar to WebAssembly Micro Runtime. Since the WebAssembly operand stack is shared between all modules and function invocations belonging to a single *M3Runtime*, as shown in Figure 3, it is not possible to share WASM memory regions, code, and metadata between parallel host threads as can be done in WAMR. Instead, a new runtime and module would need to be allocated to avoid concurrency errors. As mentioned in subsection 4.3.1, Wasm3's codebase consists of standard C code with relatively little complexity and dependencies. As such, it can be easily used as a base for extension.

4.3.3 Discussion. Wasm3 supports considerably fewer features than WebAssembly Micro Runtime because of the development's focus on a lightweight, efficient WebAssembly implementation. While this results in lower complexity and a flexible codebase, Wasm3 is not suitable for uses where the full WASM feature set is utilized because of unimplemented core proposals. Systems that consist of multiple components may require an automated, dynamic linking facility such as featured in WAMR. Furthermore, while WASM3's memory consumption is lower

Fig. 3. Wasm3 architecture

than WAMR's in the general case, its memory usage is usually higher than WAMR in *semihosted* configuration, which Wasm3 does not support.

4.4 Lua

Lua is a lightweight, efficient scripting language that can easily be embedded in C applications, designed and maintained by PUC-Rio [30]. We evaluated the standard Lua runtime in version 5.4, which is straightforward to port to bare-metal C programs. There are other commonly used, alternative Lua implementations such as LuaJIT [47] with their own features, strengths, and weaknesses.

The Lua runtime executes programs written in the Lua programming language, a dynamically typed, procedural language with support for associative arrays and automatic garbage collection [53]. Lua is an established embedded scripting language with a relatively long history since its initial release in 1993 [33] and many real-world uses.

4.4.1 Features. Some highlights of Lua's features that make it a viable framework for program virtualization on embedded systems includes:

- (1) **Dynamic loading:** Lua supports the dynamic loading of native shared libraries and other modules.
- (2) **Co-routines:** Lua supports co-routines at the language level using cooperative preemption, enabling programs to run concurrently, but not in parallel.
- (3) **A customizable standard library:** The host program can choose what parts of the library to implement and extend it with custom APIs.
- (4) **Dynamic language features:** The Lua language supports a comparatively high level of language abstraction through facilities such as first class functions, closures, dynamic error handling, associative arrays, and more.
- (5) **Garbage collection:** Lua offers incremental or generational garbage collection for freeing unused memory.

Lua's dynamic features and garbage collection allows developers to develop programs for embedded systems without having to keep track of manual memory allocations and de-allocations while being able to rely on preexisting data structures. Dynamic loading and the extensibility of the Lua language by the host allow developers to create domain-specific program environments: If a program is executed on a device with a temperature sensor, its features can be exposed to the code at runtime, and it can reflect on the sensor's availability. Lua's co-routines allow for higher throughput execution when yielding on blocking tasks such as I/O.

4.4.2 Architecture. Lua’s execution environment, including global state, code, and temporary values, is owned by a ‘lua_State’ pointer. The C host application can manage multiple states and interact with them in parallel, because the Lua implementation is fully reentrant. Using a state, the host environment can load new Lua code and add it to the existing state. By default, loaded Lua programs can access and share all global state, including variables. Lua’s standard library offers a module system for loading Lua and C dependencies at runtime. This is enabled by having shared libraries export Lua-compatible, wrapped functions. Once found, the C shared object files will be linked to the native host program dynamically before adding their function declarations to the Lua environment [53].

While Lua 5 uses register files for storing intermediate values instead of a stack, it manages an ancillary stack for data exchange between the native C host functions and Lua code [32]. When Lua calls a native function, all arguments are pushed to the ancillary stack and can be popped or modified by C code. The native function returns values to Lua by pushing them onto the same stack. Throughout Lua’s history, PUC-Rio has reduced the runtime’s dependence on a C standard library, making Lua compatible with any ANSI-C compliant host program. For example, if the host does not support allocation through malloc, the Lua runtime can be provided custom allocation functions to use instead [30].

4.4.3 Discussion. Lua was initially designed as an extension language for host applications, which could embed Lua as a scripting language through by exposing a C API [31]. The language established itself as a popular scripting language to interact with, extend, or otherwise modify larger systems [44]. It is less typical for large, self-contained applications to be entirely written in Lua, although technically possible.

The design and features of the Lua programming language make it a flexible choice for developing dynamic scripts. The language provides abstractions for powerful data structures such as dictionaries/associative arrays, closures, and exposes mechanisms to overload operators and built-in functions, or to extend custom types. Lua’s runtime provides an efficient C implementation of high-level language features, which reduces the size and overhead of Lua code that heavily relies on such abstractions. Lua programs not relying on complex features may, however, be limited by the increased interpreter’s code size, more complex memory model and garbage collection.

Lua’s design, which emphasizes script development, is not perfectly suited for the development of large systems and applications that are composed of many independently developed units. Because it is dynamically typed, more work is required to test and ensure the correctness of large codebases [45]. Lua also permits code, such as a library or module, to modify the global environment, which includes imported modules and foreign functions [53], which could break existing code by the inclusion of new subsystems or libraries. If developers need to virtualize complex systems, WebAssembly may be a better choice than Lua.

4.5 MicroPython

MicroPython is a small, efficient implementation of Python 3 that targets microcontrollers and other low-resource hardware [16]. MicroPython implements a modified version of the Python 3 programming language and does not provide the entirety of Python’s standard library. As a result, programs must usually be written for, or ported to MicroPython with idiomatic Python programs relying on features unsupported by MicroPython [15]. Nonetheless, MicroPython is one of the most popular choices for executing scripts on constrained devices, having over 6 thousand GitHub forks [17]. With an initial release of v1.0 in 2014, MicroPython sits in between the releases of Lua and WAMR.

4.5.1 Features. Many of MicroPython’s features allows for fine-tuning the runtime with regard to available hardware capabilities and resources by configuring language features. This allows developers to reduce resource usage by restricting MicroPython support to only a subset of its usual Python 3 dialect.

Fig. 4. MicroPython Architecture

- (1) Configurable garbage collection: Garbage collection can be statically enabled or disabled with feature macros and further configured at execution time by Python and C code.
- (2) Subset of the Python 3 library: MicroPython ships with support of commonly used Python modules such as `io`, `json`, `sys`, or `math`, which must be manually enabled.
- (3) Dynamic loading of native- and Python modules: MicroPython can load modules from a file system, embedded in the static binary, or over a network connection.
- (4) Tunable language implementation: Developers can enable or disable Python language features with feature macros to tune performance, for instance disabling unbound integers.

MicroPython fully manages its memory allocations. The host program initializes the runtime with a pre-allocated array that is then owned by the virtual machine's custom heap implementation. Both ancillary data structures and Python values are allocated on MicroPython's heap, so that not calls to `'malloc'` are ever performed. This results on no dynamic memory usage, as visible in subsection 5.2, but also requires developers to estimate memory usage in advance.

4.5.2 Architecture. MicroPython is not primarily designed as an extension language to embed in host applications like Lua. Internally, MicroPython keeps its state in a global variable shared between all parts of the runtime. The global state includes the heap and its metadata, interpreter state such as all loaded modules, the main module, and the currently executing python thread. The use of python threads enables concurrent, but not parallel, execution of python code sharing global data. MicroPython ensures no concurrent execution can cause undefined behavior by guarding the interpreter with a lock that is shared globally between all Python threads. Unlike WAMR and

Lua, which allow the parallel execution of code by creation of separate runtime states or execution environments, the MicroPython runtime cannot be shared between multiple host threads.

Python code can interact with native C code by wrapping C functions in Python modules. The native code must either be statically compiled and included in the binary, or embedded in *.mpy* files to be loaded at runtime similar to how Python modules are loaded. MicroPython needs to have software support for the current hardware’s ISA, if native code is loaded dynamically as part of precompiled *.mpy* files, which is currently limited to x86, arm, and xtensa [18]. Plain python modules can be loaded dynamically, or included statically in the binary image as *frozen content*.

4.5.3 Discussion. MicroPython is an established and widely available runtime for many development boards and microcontrollers [19]. The GitHub repository includes in-tree ports for dozens of boards with various chips and architectures including the esp32, esp8266, and stm32 families. While its implementation of Python allows for the flexible development of applications by developers with varying experience, it is more complicated to embed in host programs, port to new hardware, and is missing features such as parallel interpreter execution, which runtimes such as WAMR can take advantage of. Likewise, MicroPython limits memory allocation to its own heap, while both Lua and WAMR can be configured at runtime to allocate memory using either *malloc* or custom allocators. Nonetheless, the support for fine-tuning language features by the use of feature macros allows MicroPython to fit devices with varying available resources: On small, low-cost systems basic Python features like unbound integers, iterators, and garbage collection may be disabled to save resources. This of course weakens the advantage of portability that interpretation has over native execution, as end users have to write Python programs with the respective device configuration in mind.

5 Evaluating Interpreters on Embedded Systems

In this section, we compare WAMR’s interpreter execution mode and Wasm3 to each other interpreter introduced in Section 4 with regard to their overhead in both memory consumption and processing speed.

5.1 Methodology

We have chosen the Embench benchmark suite [3] as a representative set of benchmark kernels that represent embedded system workload characteristics. Contrary to synthetic benchmarks, those benchmarks expose properties that are characteristic for embedded systems. They are carefully chosen to represent the workload of embedded systems, including cryptographic, DSP and AI from the upcoming Embench 2.0 release. Each benchmark is a standalone program that is executed in a loop, and the total execution time is measured and compared.

As the benchmarks are written in C, we had to transform them to Python and Lua to be comparable. For a few benchmarks it was hard to do this, as they use pointer arithmetic, and we wanted to keep the benchmarks as close to the original as possible. While filtering out the benchmarks that could not be translated, we made sure that the subset still provides a good representation of the suite, in particular with respect to coverage of compute, control-flow and memory intensity.

Each of the benchmark programs were profiled and all runtime configurations for measuring the following static and runtime characteristics: (i) program text section size, (ii) program data section size, (iii) first run execution delay (includes runtime initialization), (iv) second run execution delay (excludes runtime initialization), (v) native stack usage, and (vi) native libc heap usage.

Each runtime was configured to use the fastest available parameters (no debug functionality etc.), in their default configurations at a balanced optimization level `-O2` and with the same compiler to ensure that they can be compared; AOT or JiT compilers were not used to execute benchmarks, see Section 6 for an evaluation of WAMR’s AoT feature on target hardware.

Fig. 5. Static memory usage of embench benchmarks in different interpreters compared to native code.

5.1.1 Profiling setup. We executed each benchmark as native code and interpreted by each runtime on an STM32L4R9-DISCO [62] evaluation board. The device features an STM32L4 microprocessor based on the Arm Cortex-M4 core, which supports the Armv7 architecture, can access 512KB of internal SRAM and contains a dedicated floating point unit (FPU). The processor was set to an 80MHz cpu clock configuration. The runtime software was compiled against newlib using the 'arm-eabi-none' gcc compiler toolchain in 'nosys' configuration. For recording heap measurements, each libc allocation and de-allocation was traced using the Arm's ITM functionality and sent to the host using a 2.5MHz SWO pin. We disabled memory tracing when capturing execution delay to ensure the results remain unaffected by its overhead. To account for potentially redundant allocations in the second benchmark execution, we only traced memory for runtime initialization and the first code invocation. Benchmarks performing IO, such as fasta, communicated via a 115200 UART connection that was set up using the same initialization procedure for each program. All measurements were generated and recorded using the same middleware in every configuration; we did not rely on debugging- or profiling capabilities included in WAMR, Lua, or MicroPython.

5.2 Results

The first interesting property to compare is the static memory footprint: Figure 5 compares the text- and data segment sizes of each tested configuration for the set of benchmarks: each evaluated runtime does not differ much between each benchmark configuration, because most required data- and code comes from the underlying runtime. Since MicroPython's heap has to be statically allocated, it is included in the resulting data segment's size. Beside this observation, the data segment size is primarily the bytecode of the virtual machine program. In a setup where multiple programs are executed or programs get larger, the text segment size containing the runtime will still stay constant.

The execution time in Figure 6 measures the required time to initialize each runtime, load the code, and execute it. The execution of the benchmarks hides the initialization and loading time and it does not have a notable impact. Each of the measurements is relative to the native execution. As clearly visible, the *interpreter* runtime approach has a significant impact on the execution time of the benchmarks, as expected. Extreme outliers are cut off in the chart for better readability.

It can be observed that the MicroPython runtime has by far the highest execution delay, while Lua is in the best case comparable to the WAMR classic interpreter, which is an in-place interpreter. But both wasm3 and the WAMR fast interpreter that translate the bytecode to an intermediate representation are faster in all cases.

Fig. 6. Relative execution time of each of the benchmarks in the embench benchmark suite (native = 1.0)

Fig. 7. Dynamic memory usage of embench benchmarks in different interpreters.

Finally, Figure 7 shows the dynamic memory usage of each runtime for the benchmarks. The dynamic memory usage is the sum of the stack usage and heap usage. As mentioned earlier, it is small in the case of MicroPython, as the heap is statically pre-allocated in the data segment. It is interesting to note that the WebAssembly runtimes seem to have a low variation in their dynamic memory usage compared to Lua.

To complete the comparison, we calculated the mean and standard deviation of the relative characteristics of each runtime, as shown in Table 2: As observed before, MicroPython is the slowest runtime, in an order of magnitude compared to the fastest runtimes. Yet, the memory footprint in terms of total static and dynamic memory usage are the smallest. Lua is faster, but still half as fast as WAMR in classic interpreter mode. wasm3 and WAMR in fast interpreter mode are the fastest at the cost of higher memory usage, but still below the memory usage of Lua.

Overall, WebAssembly delivered good runtime performance in both runtimes, with wasm3 being the best choice. Anyhow, as in the nature of interpreters, the impact on execution time is still significant compared to native execution. An alternative mode as compromise is explored in the remain of this paper.

Table 2. Mean relative characteristics

	micropython	lua	wasm3	wamr	wamr-fast
Execution time	635.99 ($\sigma = 575.52$)	176.04 ($\sigma = 115.98$)	36.86 ($\sigma = 7.99$)	86.29 ($\sigma = 23.36$)	43.34 ($\sigma = 10.92$)
Static memory size	4.15 ($\sigma = 0.42$)	4.92 ($\sigma = 0.51$)	2.83 ($\sigma = 0.24$)	3.40 ($\sigma = 0.30$)	3.51 ($\sigma = 0.31$)
Dynamic memory usage	23.81 ($\sigma = 10.88$)	141.33 ($\sigma = 126.70$)	116.86 ($\sigma = 34.75$)	70.45 ($\sigma = 19.02$)	94.88 ($\sigma = 27.61$)
Total memory usage	4.60 ($\sigma = 0.59$)	8.07 ($\sigma = 2.41$)	5.56 ($\sigma = 0.55$)	4.99 ($\sigma = 0.52$)	5.67 ($\sigma = 0.54$)

Fig. 8. Static memory usage of embench benchmarks in different WebAssembly runtimes compared to native code.

6 Evaluation of Ahead-of-Time Compilation

Another option for WebAssembly runtimes is to compile WebAssembly modules ahead of time (AoT) to native code. This approach can reduce the computational overhead significantly while still preserving isolation properties, but at the cost of decreased portability. AoT compilation is independent of compiling the original WebAssembly module with semihosting, so we benchmarked either combination of the features. Because Embench manages its own heap, no additional dynamic dependencies are introduced when compiling semihosted modules. Realistically, for Embench, the standalone configuration, which compiles libc to WASM, would not be used as it introduces memory overhead without any advantages. We nonetheless included the standalone configuration in our profiling setup for evaluating WAMR's semihosting features.

6.1 Results

Figure 8 shows the static memory usage of the benchmarks in the previously evaluated WebAssembly interpreters compared to the AoT compiled WebAssembly and the native code. It can be seen that the AoT compiled WebAssembly has a larger footprint, which is due to the extra code to handle calls from the AoT compiled code. The semihosting configuration of WAMR shows how the lack of duplication of libc code reduces the memory footprint.

Fig. 9. Relative execution time of each of the WebAssembly runtimes (native = 1.0)

Table 3. Mean, normalized Embench results

	wamr-aot	wamr-aot-semi
Execution time	2.39 ($\sigma = 0.72$)	2.19 ($\sigma = 0.70$)
Static memory size	4.54 ($\sigma = 0.39$)	4.20 ($\sigma = 0.36$)
Dynamic memory usage	89.54 ($\sigma = 24.70$)	44.16 ($\sigma = 13.93$)
Total memory usage	6.55 ($\sigma = 0.65$)	5.13 ($\sigma = 0.42$)

Figure 9 shows the relative execution time of the benchmarks with the WebAssembly interpreters and the AoT runtime. The AoT runtime is significantly faster than interpreters. The semihosting configuration of WAMR is slightly faster than the standalone configuration in cases with many libc function calls, which seems surprising with compiled code, but is an effect by less handling of guarded memory accesses from those functions.

Finally, Table 3 shows the mean results across all benchmarks. While the statistics reveal a significant standard deviation the overhead is down to as low as 70%. On the dynamic memory usage, the AoT compiled without semihosting shows a significant large memory overhead due the separate allocation and data structures inside the WebAssembly modules.

Summarized, AoT compilation of WebAssembly modules are an interesting option when targeting a low number of different embedded system architectures. But a strict requirement is that the executed code is trusted, as it may circumvent isolation mechanisms otherwise. When both criteria are met, the AoT with semihosting is a compelling setup.

7 Discussion

WebAssembly is a promising technology for application virtualization on embedded systems. Unlike other application virtual machines, such as Lua or MicroPython, WebAssembly is programming language agnostic and offers greater flexibility for application development. WASM allows developers to virtualize existing programs

in systems programming languages such as C, Rust, and more, which is enabled by WebAssembly’s low-level semantics. Furthermore, WASM is not a scripting- or extension language like Lua, and supports the idiomatic development of large-scale systems with its support of various programming languages.

Despite the high degree of flexibility and abstraction WASM offers, the performance of low-resource standalone runtimes remains competitive with alternative systems. It is important to consider that the performance of a runtime depends on the features the interpreted program relies on. Programs that make heavy use of features that are natively supported by Python or Lua are likely to have better relative performance on these platforms than those that only perform simple calculations covered by the low-level semantics of WebAssembly. Since applications for embedded systems make less frequent use of high-level features like dynamic dispatch, inheritance, or closures, they are less likely to suffer from such overhead than typical cloud- or workstation applications might.

We observed that WebAssembly Micro Runtime’s memory overhead is lower than that of Wasm3 while offering equal or better computational performance. In addition, WAMR is more actively maintained at the time of writing, fully implements the WebAssembly specification, and offers extra features such as AoT and JiT compilation. Wasm3’s biggest advantage seems to be its lightweight and simple codebase. Section 6 suggests that the computational performance of executing WebAssembly code can match that of native code when AoT compiled. Memory overhead does remain a concern in all tested configurations, even slightly increasing with usage of AoT compilation. Embedded systems can make use of importing computationally intensive functions and libc from the host program to reduce memory and processing overhead of WAMR, as observed in Section 5.

In conclusion, WebAssembly is a very promising technology for use on low-resource hardware and embedded systems that offers competitive performance compared to alternative application virtual machines while having greater flexibility. The limitation of this work is in the focus on benchmark kernels. With future work, WebAssembly needs to be evaluated in real time scenarios of dynamically loadable, autoscaling, and concurrent user- and IoT applications. However, the focus of this work was to provide a systematic comparison of WebAssembly with other interpreters in the embedded system space along with the comparison of interpreted and AoT compiled WebAssembly code.

The results indicate that WebAssembly is preferable and in case the embedded system architect trusts the loaded WebAssembly module, they should prefer AoT with semihosting. Otherwise, even WebAssembly interpreters are faster than Micropython or Lua. It has to be noted that the results are based on a single ARM platform and the benchmarks are neither exhaustive and have been ported from C to Python and Lua. While we reviewed the ported code, an optimized code could perform better.

The source code of this work and all scripts to reproduce the results are available at <https://github.com/hm-aemy/wasm-profiling>.

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